

PRAGMATIC CHARACTERISTICS OF LEXICAL UNITS

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Abstract:

In this article, lexical units in linguistics, their pragmatic features, and the semantics of lexical units are analyzed. Definitions and descriptions of concepts such as the connotative component of lexical units, text lexicon, and rational evaluation are also studied.

Key words: Lexical unit, pragmatics, connotative component, text lexicon, rational assessment.

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Introduction:

Today, in our country, attention to science and education is at a higher level than ever before. A clear example of this is the introduction of scientific councils in higher education institutions. In particular, our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev - "Science is the basis of development. Neither the state nor the society has a future that does not rely on the achievements of modern science and innovative ideas. Only through science and enlightenment, intellectual potential, well-educated personnel, we can take Uzbekistan to a new stage of development" [1] shows how important science is in the life of our society and country.

When thinking about the lexical features of pragmalinguistics, it is worth mentioning that in recent years, the expression of the structure and components of the semantics of the lexical unit in speech has attracted the special attention of researchers in various fields. One such issue is the expression of pragmatic features of lexical units through connotative components.

Pragmatic meaning expressed through connotation in the semantics of lexical units in contemporary linguistics T.V. Likhovidova (1978), N.D. Arutyunova (1979). Sternin (1985), A.N. Vstavsky (2006) and others have interpreted it in detail. In such studies, it is emphasized that the pragmatic features of the connotation expressed by the lexical unit as a specific component of human activity related to cognition, firstly, the use of linguistic signs in communication, speech evaluation functions, and secondly, they serve as an important tool in teaching communication in foreign languages.

The connotative component of lexical units means the subjective attitude of a person to people and events formed in the mind of a person who speaks this language. This attitude is expressed through language units, and determines a good, bad or neutral pragmatic attitude towards the object in the speech. Evaluative relations of people to objects of real existence are expressed as pragmatic relations in the language system, including lexical units of this language. The study of the evaluative components of the lexical meaning of the word from a pragmatic point of view required the study of a number of unsolved controversial problems. From this point of view, it is extremely important for linguists, translators, and

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Methodist teachers to determine the types and types of the evaluative component in the pragmatic sense of the lexical unit, to study their participation in the meaning of the lexical unit as a semantic component.

If we pay attention to the lexicon of the text, the pragmatic relations of the social character of the hero in the context are also involved in the evaluation of events and objects. As an object of assessment, first of all, various qualities of human nature (takasaltang, tannoq, yalqov, xayolparast; lazy, luxury, silly, dreamer); their behavior (jahldor, dangasa, yumshoq ko'ngil; angry, work-shy, calm); various social realities (g'ijillashish, nizo; dispute, scandal) are taken as a basis. Such an organic unity of emotional and evaluative components is called connotative components of lexical units.

There are two types of evaluative component of pragmatic connotation represented by lexical units:

1. Rational (intellectual) evaluation of the environment, subject, quality, virtue, events:
2. Emotional assessment of them with the help of human psyche.

A rational assessment is formed as a result of the realization of the meaning of the word in the denotative aspect. Emotional evaluation is the result of the realization of the concepts that evaluate the meaning of the word in the connotative aspect [2].

The pragmatically expressed connotative components of the meaning of the word are integrated with each other, that is, in constant contact, but each of them has quantitative peculiarities. Evaluation, along with other components of connotation, serves to increase the expressiveness (pragmatic effect) of the word's meaning, and it is they that serve to express subjective relations more strongly, more expressively, more effectively in the communicative act. In this respect, expressiveness is a pragmatic component of the meaning of the word, and it involves choosing words in the process of communication, using them according to the communication situation, and thereby having a communicative effect on the interlocutor.

When the emotional evaluative component of lexical units is called, it refers to positive (endorsement, mercy, surprise, etc.) and negative attitude (resentment, anger, disgust, rudeness) to the listener, environment, object, reality. , displeasure, anger, disgust etc) is understood.

According to Professor Sh.Safarov's research, five elements are involved in the occurrence of evaluation action, these are subject, object, basis, standard (sample) and evaluation signs. The assessment is initially created in the subject-object relationship, that is, in the process of determining whether the object is distinguished by the subject's importance, social status, attention, quantity and quality. In this process, the subject compares the property of the object being evaluated with an ideal model or standard and evaluates to what extent it corresponds or does not correspond to this standard. Finally, the assessment that has passed all the "measurements" stage is realized by means of a linguistic symbol. A rationale is required for the evaluation to occur and the evaluation action to be activated. If such a basis does not exist, mental and linguistic activity will be ineffective or even undesirable. Emotional intention lies at the logical basis of unreasonable comparison and evaluation behavior [3].

Feedback

Side panels

History

Saved

Contributions The evaluative connotative component or lexical-semantic variant of a lexical unit is usually perceived pragmatically as an implicitly expressed positive and

negative meaning. For example, *ishchan* = uninterested, lazy, lazy; *clever* = crude; orderly, disciplined = *khartanka*, *tirrancha*; hard worker = *lazy*, *clever* = stupid, well behaved = *impudent*. From the given examples, we can clearly feel the pragmatic relationship of positive and negative meanings expressed by lexical units. At the same time, the negative evaluation components of such words can also be reflected in the synonymous lines they represent. For example, Uzbek: *house-hut*, *shelter*, English: *house-hut*, Russian - *khijina*, etc. Due to this, the pragmatic evaluative connotative component makes it possible to use synonyms of different variations of the lexical meaning according to speech situations and the attitude of the speaking person to the subject.

Thus, evaluation as a specially determined pragmatic component of the meaning expressed by the word is manifested in three forms:

- 1) A lexical unit with a neutral or zero-value evaluative component;
- 2) lexical unit with an evaluative component of positive (meliorate) value;
- 3) Lexical unit with negative (derogative, pejorative) evaluative component.

Such an evaluation scale provides an opportunity to study words belonging to different lexical-semantic groups into separate lexical groups. For example, the following can be included in the evaluative lexical units expressing predicative meliorative (positive) signs of the human personality:

Beauty – *go'zallik*, pretty – *maftunkor*, sensible – *hissiyotli*, intelligent – *aqli*.

In some cases, depending on the communicative situation, the English exemplary unit with a neutral evaluative component can be used in other languages in a negative connotative sense. For example, the English word "shoemaker" is used in Russian both as the name of the owner of the profession - "sapojnik" (shoemaker), and in the negative sense of "a person who is not enthusiastic, does not know his profession well".

On the basis of predicative personal names with evaluative signs, one or more attributes and qualities characteristic of people are expressed, and the positive and negative evaluative relations of the subject, linguistic collective, representative of the social group are reflected in them.

From this point of view, lexical units representing predicative and derogative qualities of a person can be divided into two large groups:

1) Units related to negative evaluation of the subject based on social origin according to intellectual-logical signs:

A thief – *o'g'ri*;

A traitor – *sotqin*;

A liar – *yolg'onchi*

A criminal – *jinoyatchi*.

2) Evaluative lexical units with negative connotations that express intellectual signs aimed at exaggerating the qualities that are not characteristic of the subject due to emotions and mental experiences:

Hateful – *yaramas*, *muttaham*;

Flattering - *xushomadgo'y*, *dum*;

Sophist – *safsataboz*, *quruq gap sotuvchi kishi*.

Here, it should be noted that lexical units with denotative meaning form an evaluative component in the abstract sense.

It is worth noting that the words belonging to these two large groups, representing the signs of lexical units, are based on the language norms formed in national, social groups and thus express the subject's belonging to different political and social groups. Belonging to a social group of the evaluative component of the lexical unit leads to the use of the evaluative scale in different ways and in different evaluative meanings. Such a situation can be seen, for

example, in thieves' slang, when words used in the national language are used in evaluative meanings of different scales. Connotations in the semantic meaning of lexical units are also called pragmatic connotations [2].

Pragmatic connotation in the semantics of a lexical unit is divided into integral and adherent types.

Inherent connotation, recognized as a linguistic fact, represents the influence of the speaking person (author) on his interlocutor by using emotional-expressive and evaluative linguistic tools in a certain speech situation, for a specific purpose. Pragmatic factors such as place, time, time, social status of interlocutors, distance between them are involved in this process.

To sum up, the words expressing the signs of lexical units are based on the language norms formed in national, social groups and thus express the subject's belonging to different political and social groups. Belonging to a social group of the evaluative component of the lexical unit leads to the use of the evaluative scale in different ways and in different evaluative meanings.

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